

Investigating Perceived Student Engagement and Mathematics Achievement in Contextualized Lessons in TVET Schools: Moderating Effects, Motivation and Interest

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Abstract

This paper assessed the moderating effects of motivation and interest in the relationship between perceived engagement in contextualized instructions and mathematics achievement among Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) students. The study was a descriptive survey conducted in the Kumasi Metropolis of Ghana's Ashanti Region. Participants were TVET students from Kumasi Technical Institute (KTI) and the National Vocational Training Institute (NVTI). Data was collected using Likert scale style structured questionnaires. Three hundred and sixty-seven (367) students were selected from a total of four thousand five hundred (4500) Electrical Engineering Technology, Fashion Design Technology, and other programmes using simple random sampling. Data was analysed using the Structural Equation Model (SEM) in AMOS (version 23). Demographic factors such as respondents' gender, age and academic level were found to have a positive and significant influence on mathematics achievement. Perceived engagement had a significant and positive impact on mathematics achievement. Motivation significantly and positively moderated the effects of perceived engagement on mathematics achievement. Interest significantly and positively moderated the effects of perceived engagement on mathematics achievement. The study recommended that teachers should plan mathematics lessons in the context of students' career courses. Also, mathematics teaching and learning should take place in a supportive and captivating environment that heightens students' enthusiasm, and mathematics teaching and learning should be planned with the interests of learners and not dictated.

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Introduction

As TVET students undergo career training, much emphasis is placed on logical and systematic problem solving crucial for success in technical and vocational domains (Alhassan et al., 2024; Klieme, 2004; Marget & Kettler, 2019; Perrenet et al., 2000). By engaging students in contextualized mathematics instructions, the development of methodical and analytical skills to tackle complex problems in measurement, numeric computations, and geometry are enhanced. Contextualization provides the opportunity for students to experience the relevance and practical usefulness of mathematics. It is the strategy to integrate learning with students' lives and professional aspirations (Heckman, 1994; Nyaaba et al., 2023).

A major challenge faced among TVET students is poor mathematics performance in final examinations, and in examinations in related courses (Ngoveni, 2018). In comparison, TVET graduates perform worse in core mathematics than their colleagues from general education. However, contextualized instruction has emerged as a promising approach to enhance students' understanding and increase their mathematics achievement (Tindog, 2021). Students' engagement in contextualized mathematics lessons allows them to realize the practical applications of mathematical concepts in real-world situations (Beswick, 2011).

While there is substantial evidence supporting the direct effect of engagement in contextualized instruction on students' mathematics achievement (Buddo et al., 2019; Clarke & Roche, 2018; Rathburn, 2015) it is essential to acknowledge that the effect of this pedagogical approach is not uniform across all students. Fundamental psychological factors, particularly the levels of students' motivation and interest in contextualized mathematics class can lower or heighten this relationship. Motivation refers to the internal or external factors that drive individuals to engage in a specific behavior (Kwaw et al., 2024), such as learning mathematics (Deci & Ryan, 2000). In mathematics learning, motivation is the desire to excel academically, achieve personal goals, or simply enjoy the process of learning mathematical concepts.

On the other hand, interest pertains to the individual's curiosity, attraction, or liking for a particular subject or topic (Hidi & Renninger, 2006). It is conceptualized as the extent to which students find mathematical content engaging and enjoyable. When students are interested in mathematics, they are more likely to actively participate in learning activities, invest time and effort in studying, and seek opportunities to further their mathematical knowledge. Interest significantly influences students' learning experiences and outcomes in mathematics (Singh et al., 2002). Studies show that

students who exhibit high levels of interest in mathematics had higher levels of engagement and subsequent, improved performance (Tambunan et al., 2021).

Research has demonstrated that contextualized instruction is an effective strategy for improving mathematics achievement (Buddo et al., 2019; Clarke & Roche, 2018; Rathburn, 2015). It relates abstract mathematics to real-world circumstances and examples in practical terms (Arthur et al., 2017). When students connect mathematical concepts to real-world situations, they are more likely to see the relevance of mathematics in their lives, which, in turn, lead to increased engagement and better learning outcomes (Arthur et al., 2018). However, the relationship between engagement in contextualized instruction and mathematics achievement is not a one-size-fits-all scenario. Various individual psychological factors, such as motivation, contributes to this relationship, leading to differences in how students respond to contextualized mathematics instruction.

Generally, motivation and interest have both been proved to have significant influence on mathematics achievement. Students who are motivated and interested in mathematics are more likely to engage, persist, and succeed academically (Anderman & Anderman, 2010). However, how these factors interact with engagement in contextualized mathematics instruction remains slightly known among TVET's students in Ghana. This study sought to add to literature empirical knowledge of the moderating effects of motivation and interest on mathematics achievement of TVET students in contextualized mathematics teaching and learning.

Literature Review

Motivation is an essential factor that impact the learning and academic experience of students. Mathematics achievement is a crucial component of education, and students' motivation has an unswerving impact on their success in mathematics. This paper is purposed to discuss the relationship between students' motivation and mathematics achievement in a contextualize teaching and learning (CTL) environment. Many studies have scrutinized the relationship between students' motivation and mathematics achievement in diverse contexts. Researchers have found a positive correlation between students' motivation and mathematics achievement. Motivated students have the tendency to perform better academically than non-motivated ones. One study conducted by Tella (2007) investigated the relationship between students' motivation and mathematics achievement among secondary school students in Nigeria. The study found that there was a significant positive relationship between students' motivation and mathematics achievement (Hammad, et al., 2020). In another study, Pelletier (2004) explored the relationship between students' motivation and mathematics achievement among Canadian university students. The study found that students who were intrinsically motivated performed better academically than those who were extrinsically motivated or motivated. Similar results show the same findings (Tindan et al., 2023). Additionally, a meta-analysis study conducted by Wang and Eccles (2013) found a positive correlation between students' motivation and mathematics achievement across different cultural contexts (Hammad, et al., 2020). The study suggested that motivation is a critical factor in improving students' mathematics achievement.

Students' motivation plays a critical role in determining how engaged students are in their learning and how successful they are in achieving their academic goals, particularly in mathematics. Quite a few studies have investigated the relationship

between student motivation, engagement, and mathematics achievement. One such study by Middleton and Spanias (1999) reveals that students who had enough and high levels of intrinsic motivation in mathematics attain greater engagement and higher achievement; this points out the importance of cultivating intrinsic motivation in students to develop their engagement and achievement. A study conducted by Xia et al. (2022) also examined the relationship between students' motivation, engagement, and mathematics achievement in the context of project-based learning. They found that students who had higher levels of motivation and engagement were more successful in completing projects and achieving higher scores in mathematics assessments.

Other studies have also emphasized the role of teachers in promoting students' motivation and engagement in mathematics. For example, a study by Durksen and colleagues (2017) found that when teachers used motivational strategies such as providing opportunities for student choice and autonomy, students were more engaged and achieved higher scores in mathematics. Overall, these studies highlight the importance of students' motivation in promoting engagement and achievement in mathematics. Teachers can play a critical role in fostering students' motivation by providing opportunities for student autonomy, choice, and project-based learning (Tindan et al., 2022). By understanding the relationship between student motivation, engagement, and achievement in mathematics, educators can develop effective strategies for improving student outcomes in this critical subject.

CTL are an instructional method that connects academic content to real-world conditions and experiences, making learning more relevant and engaging for students. Research has revealed that students' interest is a key factor in their academic achievement, including in mathematics. In the context of CTL, students' interest in mathematics can be boosted through the use of real-world set-ups and applications, which can help students to understand the practical value of mathematical concepts and skills. Several studies have investigated the relationship between students' interest and mathematics achievement in CTL. For example, a study by Bottge (1999) found that students who participated in a contextualized algebra program had higher achievement scores and more positive attitudes towards mathematics than those who received traditional algebra instruction. The authors suggest that the contextualized approach helped students see the relevance of algebra to their lives and motivated them to learn more effectively. The contextualized course included real-world examples and applications of mathematical concepts, which helped students see the practical value of mathematics and motivated them to learn. The contextualized approach helped students see the relevance of science to their lives and motivated them to learn more effectively. Finally, these studies suggest that student interest is an important factor in mathematics achievement in CTL, and that the use of real-world scenarios and applications can enhance students' interest and motivation, leading to improved mathematics achievement.

CTL are an approach to education that connects academic content to real-world situations, problems, and applications. This approach has been found to be effective in increasing students' interest and motivation, especially in STEM subjects like mathematics. When students see the relevance and importance of mathematics in their daily lives and future careers, they are more likely to engage with the subject and achieve better outcomes. Several studies have investigated the relationship between students' interest and mathematics achievement in CTL. For example, a study by Galla and Wood (2012) found that the use of contextualized math tasks improved students'

interest and engagement in mathematics, as well as their mathematics achievement. The authors suggest that the use of real-world examples and problems can help students see the value of mathematics and develop a deeper understanding of the subject. The author suggests that the contextualized curriculum helped students connect algebraic concepts to real-world situations, leading to improved understanding and achievement.

Another study by Valenzuela (2018) investigated the impact of a contextualized mathematics program on student interest and achievement in middle school. The authors found that students who participated in the program had higher interest and achievement scores than those who received traditional instruction. The authors suggest that the use of real-world examples and problems helped students develop a positive attitude towards mathematics and see the relevance of the subject to their lives. Finally, these studies suggest that student interest is an important factor in mathematics achievement in CTL, and that the use of real-world examples and problems can enhance student interest and motivation, leading to improved mathematics achievement.

Objectives and Research Hypothesis

The study sought to achieve the following objectives;

1. examine the relationship between students' perceived engagement in contextualized instructions and mathematics achievement among TVET students.
2. investigate the moderating effects of students' interest on mathematics achievement.

Research Hypothesis

H₁: Students' perceived engagement in contextualized lessons have direct positive effect on mathematics achievement.

H₂: Students' interest moderates the relationship between students' perceived engagement and mathematics achievement in contextualized teaching and learning.

H₃: Students' motivation moderates the relationship between students' perceived engagement and mathematics achievement in contextualized teaching and learning.

Conceptual Framework

The conceptual framework of the present study is shown on Figure 1. Figure 1 comprises four variables. Perceived engagement is independent variable, motivation and interest are the moderators, and mathematics achievement is the dependent variable. H₁ is the hypothesis for the direct effects of perceived engagement on mathematics achievement, and H₂ and H₃ are the hypotheses for the moderating effects of motivation and interest respectively.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

Methods

The population of the study was TVET students in the Kumasi Metropolis offering electrical engineering technology, fashion design technology, and other courses in the Kumasi Technical Institute (K.T. I) and the National Vocational Training Institute (NVTI) as shown in Table 1.

Table 1. The Population Distribution According to School and Program

Name of school	Electricals	Fashion	Totals
KTI	2000	1200	3200
NVTI	800	500	1300
TOTALS	2800	1700	4500

Source: School Register (2023)

Sample and sampling techniques are an essential part of quantitative research. A sample is a subset of the population that is selected to participate in a study, and sampling techniques are the methods used to select the sample. The goal of sampling is to select a sample that is representative of the population so that the results of the study can be generalized to the population. The researcher selected two TVET schools by cluster sampling method. This technique involves selecting groups of participants around a given geographical area. For proximity reasons, this procedure was appropriate since NVTI and KTI are the closest in the Kumasi Metropolis. The second stage of the sample selection involved using random sampling technique to pick participants from the schools per the proportion of the student's population. Random sampling involves selecting participants from the population at random, giving each member of the population an equal chance of being selected, in this case, $\frac{3200}{4500} \times 367 = 261$ participants were taken from KTI, where as $\frac{1300}{4500} \times 367 = 106$ students were taken from NVTI. In all, a total of 367 respondents used in the study. This number was determined by the Slovin's formula for sample size allocation. The Slovin's formula is given by $n = \frac{N}{1+Ne^2}$; where n = sample size, N = population size, and e = margin of error at 95% confidence level.

The study used structured questionnaires on Likert scale to collect data (Bannor, Boadu, & Arthur, 2023). The items were measured on an evaluative continuum ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree. The instrument was divided into five sections. The first section consisted of three items to collect demographic information of participants including age, gender and course of study. The second part of the instrument was divided into four sections according the constructs under investigation. Under each construct, 10 items were used to collect responses. Items used to measure engagement and motivation were adapted from (Boadu et al., 2023). Items used to measure interest were adapted from (Arthur, Appiah et al., 2022). Items used to measure mathematics achievement were adapted from (Boadu et al., 2023). The researcher sought the consent of the school authority, and participants to ensure data protection, and secrecy.

Measures and Questionnaire

The survey utilized structured questionnaires featuring standardized items, and it employed a closed-ended format with a response scale ranging from strongly disagree to strongly agree (Bannor, & Obeng, 2024). Prior to the main survey, a pilot study was

conducted to identify necessary revisions in the questionnaire. The survey consisted of four sections, with the first section collecting demographic data such as age, gender, academic level, and course of study (Bannor, & Obeng, 2024). The second section included four items adapted from Arthur et al. (2018) to assess perceived mathematics connections, while the third section consisted of three items adapted from Arthur et al. (2022) to capture students' opinions on the history of mathematics concepts. The final section measured students' perceived mathematics motivation using four items adapted from Lang and Fries (2006).

Validity and Reliability Analysis

The study computed confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) by AMOS (version 23) to assess the fitness of the measurement model. During the confirmatory factor analysis, factor loadings were assessed for each indicator on the scale (Bannor, Boadu, & Arthur, 2023). Factor loadings were ensured above 0.50 ($>.50$). Due to lower factor loadings, 17 items were exited. To enhance model fitness, modification indices were assessed at their respective benchmarks according to Hu and Bentler (1999) criterion for CMIN/DF, GFI, CFI, TLI, SRMR, and RMSEA as shown on Table 2 (Bannor, Boadu, & Arthur, 2023). Figure 2 displays the structure of the CFA.

Table 2. Results of Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Fit Indices: <i>CMIN = 320.452; DF = 203; CMIN/DF = 1.579; CFI = 0.945; TLI = 0.937; RMR = 0.063; RMSEA = 0.040; PCLOSE = 0.973; GFI=0.925</i>	Factor Loadings
INTEREST (I): CA=0.783; CR=0.791; AVE=0.434	
(I1): I find mathematics interesting and enjoyable.	.561
(I2): I think mathematics is important for my future.	.667
(I3): I like learning about real-life applications of mathematics.	.638
(I4): I feel motivated to learn mathematics.	.774
(I5): Students' level of interest impacts their overall achievement in the subject.	.634
ENGAGEMENT (E): CA=0.816; CR=0.816; AVE=0.425	
(E4): I feel that mathematics lessons taught in my TVET institution are relevant to my needs	.627
(E5): Level of engagement impacts achievement.	.593
(E6): Engagement improve academic performance.	.694
(E7): I feel engaged during classroom discussions and activities.	.649
(E8): I believe engagement influences understanding and retention of course material.	.678
(E9): The level of engagement impacts my learning outcome.	.667
MOTIVATION (M): CA=0.713; CR=0.714; AVE=0.334	
(M4): I set goals for myself to improve my mathematics skills.	.581
(M6): Personal interest motivates me to do well in mathematics.	.592
(M7): Desire to pursue maths related career motivates in mathematics.	.624
(M8): The use of technology motivates my learning of mathematics.	.553
(M9): I am motivated to improve my mathematics skills.	.534
ACHIEVEMENT (A): CA=0.778; CR=0.778; AVE=0.370	
(A5): I believe student engagement in CTL affects mathematics achievement.	.538
(A6): I believe teacher support in CTL affects mathematics achievement.	.610
(A7): The level of difficulty of mathematics concepts affects mathematics achievement.	.573
(A8): The relationship between engagement and achievement is moderated by the level of interest.	.625
(A9): The relationship between engagement and achievement is moderated by the level of interest.	.642
(A10): The relationship between engagement and achievement is moderated by the level of interest in real-world applications of mathematics.	.611

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Figure 2. Diagram of Confirmatory Factor Analysis
Source: Field Survey (2023)

Construct reliability of the scale was determined using Cronbach alpha and composite reliability. The study ensured that Cronbach alpha for each variable was maintained at the required threshold of 0.70 (Cronbach,1951; Bannor, Boadu, & Arthur, 2023). Alpha reliability of Interest (I), Motivation (M), perceived Achievement (A), and perceived Engagement (E) were .927, .923, .914 and .924 respectively. Composite reliabilities were computed from indicators factor loadings by the formula: $(\sum \lambda)^2 / [(\sum \lambda)^2 + \sum (1 - \lambda^2)]$; where λ indicates factor loadings of indicators under each variable. Composite reliabilities ranged from 0.714 to 0.816, which were above the required benchmark of .70. Therefore, construct reliability was established as shown on Table 3.

Table 3. Construct Reliability

Constructs	Cronbach Alpha	Composite Reliability	Number of Items
Interest (I)	0.783	0.791	5
Motivation (M)	0.713	0.714	5
Achievement (A)	0.778	0.778	6
Engagement (E)	0.816	0.816	6

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Convergent validity measures the degree to which indicators of a variable correlate enough. Convergent validity of the variables was identified by calculating Average Variance Extracted (AVE) (Sujati et al., 2020). The average variance extracted of Interest and Engagement were above closer to the minimum value of 0.50 (Mendes & Cirillo, 2021). Interest and Engagement met the required convergent validity whereas

Motivation and Achievement did not meet the required convergent validity as shown on Table 3.

Discriminant validity determines the extent to which indicators in different constructs are uncorrelated (Trochim & Donnelly, 2001). Discriminant validity was assessed using Fornell and Larker Criterion (Fornell & Larker, 1981). According to this criterion, the smallest value of the square root of the AVEs should be greater than the largest correlation coefficient (Bannor, & Obeng, 2024). Table 4 shows that the smallest value of the square root of the AVEs was 0.578, while the highest correlation coefficient was 0.648. Therefore, discriminant validity was not attained.

Table 4. Discriminant Validity

Variables	AVE	I	M	E	A
I	0.434	<u>0.659</u>			
M	0.334	0.475**	<u>0.578</u>		
E	0.425	0.504**	0.494**	<u>0.652</u>	
A	0.370	0.417**	0.596**	0.648**	<u>0.608</u>

Note: ** ~ P-value significant at 1% (0.01); $\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ are bold and underlined

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Results

A structural equation model was generated in AMOS. The structural equation model was used to estimate the relationships between the variables under study (Bannor, Boadu, & Arthur, 2023). The model fitted for the data as CMIN/DF, Goodness-of-Fit Indices (GFI), Tucker and Lewis Index (TLI), Confirmatory Fit Index (CFI), Standard Root Mean Square (SRMR), and Root Mean Square Error Approximation (RMSEA) were all ensured within their tolerable ranges (Hu & Bentler, 1999).

The study explored the direct impact of perceived Engagement in contextualized instructions on the mathematics Achievement of TVEIT students. The impact of perceived Engagement (E) on Achievement (A) was positive and significant (Estimate = 0.457, C.R. = 4.153, P-value < 0.001). Similarly, the study also examined the effects of respondents' demographics on their Achievement. Gender and Level positively and significantly had effects on Achievement. Program on the other hand, produced negative and significant effect on Achievement. Conversely, Age produced positive but insignificant effect on Achievement. The results of direct effects are displayed on Table 5.

Table 5. Direct Path Estimates

Direct Paths	UnStd. Estimate	C.R.	S.E.	P-value
A<---Age	0.017	0.215	0.077	0.829
A<---Gender	0.212	2.778	0.212	0.005**
A<---Program	-0.031	-0.680	0.045	0.497**
A<---Level	0.189	2.889	0.065	0.004**
A<---E	0.481	5.219	0.092	***
Model Fit Indices: <i>CMIN</i> = 462.715; <i>DF</i> = 241; <i>CMIN/DF</i> = 1.920; <i>CFI</i> = .922; <i>TLI</i> = .911; <i>RMR</i> = .058; <i>RMSEA</i> = .049; <i>PCLOSE</i> = .624				

Note: ** Significant at 5%; *** Significant at 1%

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Figure 3. Diagram of Direct Effects Analysis

Source: Field Survey (2023)

The study examined the moderating effect of interest (I) on the relationship between perceived engagement (E) in contextualized instructions and mathematics achievement (A) of TVET students. Table 6 shows that the interaction effect was positive and significant (Estimate = 0.062, C.R. = 1.972, P-value = 0.049).

Table 6. Results of Interaction Effects of Interest

Relationship	Estimate	C.R.	P-Value
A \leftarrow E	0.409	7.878	***
A \leftarrow I	0.163	3.309	***
A \leftarrow E \times I	0.062	1.972	0.049**

Note: ** Significant at 5%; *** Significant at 1%

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Figure 4. Diagram of Interaction Effects Analysis

Source: Field Survey (2023)

The study investigated the moderating effect of motivation (M) on the relationship between perceived engagement (E) in contextualized instructions and mathematics achievement (A) of TVET students. The results as revealed on Table 7 shows that the interaction effect was positive and significant (Estimate = 0.090, C.R. =3.233, P-value = 0.001).

Table 7. Moderating Effects of Motivation

Relationship	Estimate	C.R.	P-value
A<---E	0.379	8.140	***
A<---M	0.251	5.230	***
A<--- E×M	0.090	3.233	0.001***

Note: ** Significant at 5%; *** Significant at 1%

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Figure 5. Diagram of Interaction Effects Analysis

Source: Field Survey (2023)

Discussion

Dotterer et al. (2007), conducted a thorough investigation that look at the connections between extracurricular activities, involvement in the classroom, and academic outcomes. These ties span several academic fields, maybe including achievement in mathematics. The relationship between students' perceptions of their engagement in arithmetic and their mathematical achievement is a key area of attention in educational research. Perceived engagement, which refers to the subjective experience of being absorbed, attentive, and actively involved in learning activities, is strongly related to participation in the learning process, great curiosity, and sincere dedication. A significant impact on academic results, particularly in terms of math achievements, can be seen by the degree of student's involvement. The relationship between students' assessments of their school environment, their level of engagement, and their academic achievements is clarified through an investigation made in the study done by Wang and Holcombe (2010). This inquiry spans a number of academic disciplines, including mathematics.

Researchers assert that students' perceived engagement is one of the key elements influencing their success in mathematics when given contextualized instructions. This inference is consistent with the findings of the current study that the relationship between student perceived engagement and mathematics achievement in contextualized teaching-learning environment is positive and significant (Estimate = 0.457, C.R. = 4.153, P-value < 0.001). Review of relevant literature showed that this result is statistically supported by a number of writings and contributes greatly to the body of knowledge. Studies have consistently shown that higher levels of engagement in contextualized instructions are associated with better academic achievement (Appleton et al., 2006; Fredricks et al., 2004; Kwaw & Kwakye, 2024). In the context of mathematics education, a study by Wang and Holcombe (2010) found a positive relationship between students' engagement and mathematics achievement in contextualized teaching-learning. Similarly, a study by Fung and colleagues, (2018), reveal that better levels of academic accomplishment were connected with students who were more involved, with cognitive engagement having the largest association.

The moderating effects of student interest in contextualization on the relationship between student engagement and mathematics performance demonstrate a remarkable synergy that improves students' learning experiences and academic achievements. When student interest in contextualization is combined with high levels of student engagement, the impact on mathematics success surpasses what would be predicted if each element worked alone (Symonds et al., 2019). This dynamic interaction of interest and engagement in contextualized teaching-learning has important implications for educators and policymakers seeking to improve mathematics education.

One of the greatest benefits identified among students who find mathematics interesting and applicable to real-world problems is increased engagement (Acquandoh et al., 2022; Bornaa et al., 2022; Kelley & Knowles, 2016). Students become more eager and passionate about investigating the subject matter when they have a genuine interest in contextualized learning. This intrinsic incentive motivates students to actively take part in math lessons, resulting in higher participation in classroom activities, debates, and problem-solving assignments (Owusu et al., 2022; Paris & Winograd, 2003). The combination of interest and engagement creates a favorable and supportive learning environment in which students are eager to devote cognitive effort and time in understanding and tackling mathematical issues. As a results, the present findings agree with that of (Wang et al., 2021).

Interest-driven contextualization helps students learn mathematical topics more deeply (Chan et al., 2018). Students can better recount the subject content and visualize its practical implications by relating abstract mathematical ideas to real-life circumstances as identified in (Arthur et al., 2017). This enhanced comprehension is the outcome of cognitive processing fueled by students' interest and eagerness to investigate contextualized challenges. As a result, students are more likely to retain information and use it successfully in many situations, boosting learning transfer and long-term retention of mathematical concepts per the findings of (Blumenfeld et al., 1991). The interaction of interest and student engagement helps students overcome arithmetic phobia which have negative impact on students' performance and confidence (Furner & Gonzalez-dehass, 2011). Students' emotional experiences become more positive when they find math relevant and enjoyable in real-life circumstances, lowering anxiety linked with abstract mathematical concepts. This favourable emotional link promotes their interest in the topic and gives them comfort and confidence when confronted with mathematical obstacles.

Contextualized math problems frequently need creative and critical thinking in order to meet real-world concerns. Students who are interested in these issues are more likely to use inventive problem-solving tactics and think critically to discover answers. This promotes the development of valuable problem-solving and analytical abilities that go beyond the classroom (Bentley, 2012). The favourable relationship between interest, engagement, and contextualization fosters students' confidence and ingenuity in approaching complicated issues. The positive interaction effects of student motivation in contextualization on student engagement and mathematics achievement highlight the critical role that student motivation in contextualized learning experiences play in education, especially in mathematics. When this characteristic is integrated properly, it results in considerable gains in students' mathematical engagement and overall academic accomplishment.

Student motivation is essential for achieving excellent learning outcomes (Arthur et al., 2022; Eriyanto et al., 2021). Motivated students participate more actively in their studies, have a good attitude toward learning, and show perseverance in the face of adversity (Zimmerman & Schunk, 2012). A study conducted by Hutajulu et al. (2019) showed that motivated students are more likely to devote time and effort to understanding mathematical ideas and problem solving in the setting of mathematics. Per the review of Reyes et al. (2019), contextualization relates mathematics to real-world circumstances, personal experiences, or students' hobbies, it bridges the gap between abstract ideas and specific applications, giving students a clear grasp of the relevance and value of what they are studying. This relevant relationship between mathematical principles and real-world applications makes learning more interesting and captivating (Arthur et al., 2018).

The results are consistent with Martin (2007). Student engagement and mathematics achievement benefit from the combination of student motivation in contextualization. For starters, it increases students' relevancy and enthusiasm in mathematics. Students are more likely to find math interesting and worthwhile to learn if they can understand how it pertains to their life. This inner desire promotes enhanced engagement and active participation. Active learning tactics like problem-solving tasks and real-world applications normally rests on recommended levels of motivation. As a results, the findings agree with Hutajulu et al. (2019). These strategies enable students to participate actively in their learning, fostering critical thinking and problem-solving abilities. As a result, students who are actively involved gain a greater comprehension and memory of mathematical topics (Arthur et al., 2018).

Additionally, the findings support Jang (2008) according to which the combination of student motivation and active engagement gives students a sense of autonomy and ownership over their learning. Motivated students are more inclined to take ownership of their education, seek more resources, and investigate math outside of the classroom as they perceive the real-world applicability of mathematics (Hannula, 2006). This self-directed method to learning can lead to increased understanding and numerical proficiency. Motivation in contextualized environment dispel the myth that math is a difficult and dull topic. As students succeed and enjoy contextualized math activities, they gain self-confidence and reduce math fear, increasing their engagement and achievement in the subject.

Conclusions

The key role of student interest as a significant moderator in the connection between perceived student engagement and mathematics achievement is highlighted by the results. When the subject holds authentic interest for students, their level of engagement has a more substantial impact on their achievement in mathematics. This underscores the significance of cultivating and fostering student interest to optimize the advantageous outcomes of heightened engagement.

The importance of student interest as a moderator in the relationship between math achievement and perceived student engagement is demonstrated by the findings. When students have a genuine interest in the subject, their degree of engagement has a more significant effect on their mathematical ability. This emphasizes the importance of cultivating and fostering student interest in order to maximize the positive effects of increased engagement.

According to the study, students' interest in mathematics is increased by contextualized teaching and learning approaches. When mathematical topics are introduced in settings that are relevant to their career goals, the degree of engagement of TVET students' increases. This finding supports the idea that student engagement in mathematics as a whole has the potential to be increased by the addition of relevant examples and real-world applications.

Strengthened influence of engagement on their mathematical achievement is seen by motivated students while studying and teaching in a situation that is relevant to them. It is revealed that, in the contextually personalized mathematics learning process, motivated students who actively participate are more likely than their less motivated counterparts to achieve increased levels of achievement in the subject.

Recommendations

In Ghana's TVET (Technical and Vocational Education and Training) schools, it is crucial for teachers to plan mathematics lessons in the context of students' career courses. This recommendation stems from the understanding that mathematics can sometimes appear abstract and disconnected from real-world applications, leading to disinterest or difficulties in comprehension among students. By integrating mathematics into the specific career courses students are pursuing, educators can make the subject more relevant and meaningful. Mathematics teaching and learning should take place in supportive and captivating environment that heightens students' enthusiasm. Mathematics teaching and learning should be planned at the interest of learners and not dictated.

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Author Contributions

Conceptualization and study design: Akansiaba, Boateng, Appiagyei; Data collection and experiments: Akansiaba, Boateng, Appiagyei, Adiku; Data analysis and

interpretation: Akansiaba, Boateng, Appiagyei, Adiku, Kwakye; Validation: Review and editing: Akansiaba, Boateng, Appiagyei, Adiku; Visualization and figures: Akansiaba, Boateng, Appiagyei, Adiku, Kwakye; Writing the original draft: Akansiaba, Boateng, Appiagyei, Kwakye

Author's contribution

All author contributed in making this study a success.

Author's declaration

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References

Alhassan, I., Kwakye, D. O., Essuman, I. B., Malik, A. T., Hudu, A., & Iddrisu, A. R. (2024). Junior High School Mathematics Teachers' Perceived Knowledge of Problem-Solving and Practices of Teaching Mathematics Through Problem-Solving in the Tamale Metropolis. *East African Journal of Education Studies*, 7(1), 500-515. <https://doi.org/10.37284/eajes.7.1.1835>

Anderman, E. M., Anderman, L. H., Yough, M. S., & Gimbert, B. G. (2010). Value-added models of assessment: Implications for motivation and accountability. *Educational Psychologist*, 45(2), 123-137.

Arthur, Y. D., Appiah, S. K., Amo-Asante, K., & Asare, B. (2022). Modeling student's interest in mathematics: Role of history of mathematics, peer-assisted learning, and student's perception. *EURASIA Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 18(10).

Arthur, Y. D., Asiedu-Addo, S., & Assuah, C. (2017). Connecting Mathematics to Real Life Problem using Instructor Quality and Availability, Mathematics Facility and Teacher Motivation for Prediction. *International Journal of Scientific Research in Education*, 10(3), 311-324.

Arthur, Y. D., Boadu, S. K., & Asare, B. (2022). Effects of Peer Tutoring, Teaching Quality and Motivation on Mathematics Achievement in Senior High Schools Examples of Projective Resolution of Lengths $3n/4n$ That Do Not Satisfy Homological Properties of Nakayama Algebra. View project Modeling mathematic. *Int J Edu Sci*, 37(1-3), 35-43. <https://doi.org/10.31901/24566322.2022/37.1-3.1221>

Arthur, Y. D., Owusu, E. K., Asiedu-Addo, S., & Arhin, A. K. (2018). Connecting Mathematics To Real-Life Problems: A Teaching Quality That Improves Students' Mathematics Interest. *IOSR Journal of Research & Method in Education*, 8(4), 65-71. <https://doi.org/10.9790/7388-0804026571>

Bannor, G., Boadu, S., & Arthur, Y. (2023). Effects of teaching quality, teaching competence, and mathematics connection on mathematics achievement motivation

among senior high school students in Ghana. *Matrix Science Mathematic*, 7, 63-68. <https://doi.org/10.26480/msmk.02.2023.63.68>

Bannor, A., & Obeng. (2024) Effects of Perceived Mathematics Connection on Mathematics Motivation: Mediating Role of History of Mathematics Concepts. *International Journal of Mathematics and Mathematics Education (IJMME)*, 2(1), 1-14 <https://doi.org/10.56855/ijmme.v2i1.898>

Bentley, T. (2012). *Learning beyond the classroom: Education for a changing world*. Routledge.

Beswick, K. (2011). Putting context in context: An examination of the evidence for the benefits of 'contextualised'tasks. *International journal of science and mathematics education*, 9, 367-390.

Blumenfeld, P. C., Soloway, E., Marx, R. W., Krajcik, J. S., Guzdial, M., & Palincsar, A. (1991). Motivating_project_based_learning_Sustai.pdf. *Educational Psychologist*, 26(3 & 4), 369–398.

Boadu, S. K., Arthur, Y. D., & Bonyah, E. (2023). Mediation and moderation effects of motivation and teaching quality on the relationship between peer tutoring and mathematics achievement. *Journal of Mathematics and Science Teacher*, 3(2), 1–14.

Bottge, B. A. (1999). Effects of contextualized math instruction on problem solving of average and below-average achieving students. *The Journal of Special Education*, 33(2), 81.

Buddo, C., Sherriffe, D., & McCarthy-Curvin, A. (2019). Realistic Mathematics Education (RME) Approach: Exploring Solving Differential Equations in the Learning of Calculus at The University of the West Indies, Mona. *Journal of Education & Development in the Caribbean*, 18(1).

Chan, T., Looi, C., Chen, W., Wong, L., Chang, B., Liao, C. C. Y., Cheng, H., Chen, Z., Liu, C., Kong, C., Jeong, H., Mason, J., So, H., Murthy, S., Chan, T., Chang, B., & Chen, Z. (2018). Interest-Driven Creator Theory: Towards a Theory of Learning Design for Asia in the Twenty-First Century National Institute of Education, Nanyang Technological University, Singapore. *Journal of Computers in Education*, 5(4), 435–461.

Clarke, D., & Roche, A. (2018). Using contextualized tasks to engage students in meaningful and worthwhile mathematics learning. *The Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 51, 95-108.

Deci, E. L., & Ryan, R. M. (2000). The "What" and "Why" of Goal Pursuits: Human Needs and the Self-Determination of Behavior. *Psychological Inquiry*, 11(4), 227–268.

Dotterer, A. M., McHale, S. M., & Crouter, A. C. (2007). Implications of out-of-school activities for school engagement in African American adolescents. *Journal of Youth and Adolescence*, 36(4), 391–401.

Durksen, T. L., Way, J., Bobis, J., Anderson, J., Skilling, K., & Martin, A. J. (2017). Motivation and engagement in mathematics: a qualitative framework for teacher-student interactions. *Mathematics Education Research Journal*, 29, 163-181.

Eriyanto, M. G., Roesminingsih, M. V., & Soeherman, I. K. (2021). The Effect of Learning Motivation on Learning Independence and Learning Outcomes of Students in the Package C Equivalence Program. *International Journal of Recent Educational Research*, 2(4), 455–467.

- Fornell, C. G., & Larcker, D. F. (1981). Evaluating structural equation models with unobservable variables and measurement error. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18(1), 39–50.
- Fredricks, J. A., Blumenfeld, P. C., & Paris, A. H. (2004). School engagement: Potential of the concept, state of the evidence. *Review of Educational Research*, 74(1), 59-109.
- Fung, Francis & Tan, Cheng & Chen, Gaowei. (2018). Student engagement and mathematics achievement: Unraveling main and interactive effects. *Psychology in the Schools*, 55. 10.1002/pits.22139.
- Furner, J. M., & Gonzalez-dehass, A. (2011). How do Students' Mastery and Performance Goals Relate to Math Anxiety? *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science & Technology Education*, 7(4), 227–242.
- Galla, B. M., & Wood, J. J. (2012). The role of contextualization in understanding mathematics: A study of student responses to word problems. *Journal of Mathematical Behavior*, 31(3), 363-372. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jmathb.2012.02.003>
- Hammad, S., Graham, T., Dimitriadis, C., & Taylor, A. (2020). Effects of a successful mathematics classroom framework on students' mathematics self-efficacy, motivation, and achievement: a case study with freshmen students at a university foundation programme in Kuwait. *International Journal of Mathematical Education in Science and Technology*, 53(6), 1502–1527. <https://doi.org/10.1080/0020739X.2020.1831091>
- Hannula, M. S. (2006). Motivation in Mathematics: Goals Reflected in Emotions Author (s): Markku S . Hannula Source: Educational Studies in Mathematics , Oct ., 2006 , Vol . 63 , No . 2 , Affect in Mathematics Education: Exploring Theoretical Frameworks: A PME Special Iss. *Springer*, 63(2), 165–178. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10649-005-9019-8>
- Heckman, P. E., & Weissglass, J. (1994). Contextualized mathematics instruction: Moving beyond recent proposals. *For the learning of Mathematics*, 14(1), 29-33.
- Hidi, S., & Renninger, K. A. (2006). The four-phase model of interest development. *Educational psychologist*, 41(2), 111-127.
- Hutajulu, M., Wijaya, T. T., Hidayat, W., Info, A., & Solving, P. (2019). The Effect of Mathematical Disposition and Learning Motivation on Problem Solving: *Infinity*, 8(2), 229–238.
- Jang, H. (2008). Supporting Students' Motivation, Engagement, and Learning During an Uninteresting Activity. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 100(4), 798–811. <https://doi.org/10.1037/a0012841>
- Jonas W. B. L., & Stefan F. (2006). Revised Achievement Motives Scale. *European Journal of Psychological Assessment*, 22(3):216–224, <https://doi.org/10.1027/1015-5759.22.3.216>
- Kelley, T. R., & Knowles, J. G. (2016). A conceptual framework for integrated STEM education. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 3(1). <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-016-0046-z>
- Klieme, E. (2004). Assessment of cross-curricular problem-solving competencies. *Comparing learning outcomes. International assessments and education policy*, 81-107.

- Kwaw, R. N., Kwakye, D. O., & Appiah, S. (2024). Teacher Expectation and Students' Learning Behaviour: The Role of School Location. *Open Access Journal of Education and Language Studies*, 2(3):555588, <https://doi.org/10.19080/OAJELS.2024.2555588>
- Kwaw, R., N., & Kwakye, D. O. (2024). Teachers' knowledge and use of behaviour modification strategies in classroom management: Does gender matter? *Frontiers of Contemporary Education*, 5(1), 38-50. <https://doi.org/10.22158/fce.v5n1p38>
- Lee, J. (1951). Cronbach: Coefficient Alpha and The Internal Structure of Tests. *Psychometrika*, 16(3).
- Li-tze Hu & Peter M. Bentler (1999) Cutoff criteria for fit indexes in covariance structure analysis: Conventional criteria versus new alternatives, *Structural Equation Modeling. A Multidisciplinary Journal*, 6(1), 1-55, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10705519909540118>
- Marget, K. C., & Kettler, T. (2019). Teachers' perception of STEM integration and education: a systematic literature review. *International Journal of STEM education*, 6(1), 1-16.
- Martin, A. J. (2007). Examining a multidimensional model of student motivation and engagement using a construct validation approach. *British Journal of Educational Psychology* (2007), 77, 413–440. <https://doi.org/10.1348/000709906X118036>
- Mendes dos Santos, P., & Cirillo, M. Â. (2021). Construction of the average variance extracted index for construct validation in structural equation models with adaptive regressions. *Communications in Statistics: Simulation and Computation*. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03610918.2021.1888122>
- Middleton, J. A., & Spanias, P. A. (1999). Motivation for achievement in mathematics: Findings, generalizations, and criticisms of the research. *Journal for research in Mathematics Education*, 30(1), 65-88.
- Ngoveni, M. A. (2018). *Factors linked to poor performance for NC (V) Level 2 mathematics students* (Doctoral dissertation, University of Pretoria).
- Nyaaba, R. A., Abdul-Gafaar, S., Akulga, C. A., & Kwakye, D. O. (2023). Assessing the impact of continuous professional development of teachers and its effects on satisfaction, achievement, and engagement: Colleges of Education, Northern Ghana. *Journal of Educational and Teaching Methods*, 2(2), 41-57. <https://doi.org/10.58425/jetm.v2i2.178>
- Paris, S. G., & Winograd, P. (2003). The Role of Self-Regulated Learning in Contextual Teaching: In *A Commissioned Paper for the U.S. Department of Education Project Preparing Teachers to Use Contextual Teaching and Learning Strategies To Improve Student Success In and Beyond School*.
- Pelletier, L. G., Seguin-Levesque, C., & Legault, L. (2004). Pressure from above and pressure from below as determinants of teachers' motivation and teaching behaviors. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 96(1), 89–99. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.96.1.89>
- Perrenet, J. C., Bouhuijs, P. A., & Smits, J. G. (2000). The suitability of problem-based learning for engineering education: theory and practice. *Teaching in higher education*, 5(3), 345-358.

- Rathburn, M. K. (2015). Building connections through contextualized learning in an undergraduate course on scientific and mathematical literacy. *International Journal for the Scholarship of Teaching and Learning*, 9(1), n1.
- Singh, K., Granville, M., & Dika, S. (2002). Mathematics and science achievement: Effects of motivation, interest, and academic engagement. *The Journal of educational research*, 95(6), 323-332.
- Sujati, H., Sajidan, Akhyar, M., & Gunarhadi. (2020). Testing the construct validity and reliability of curiosity scale using confirmatory factor analysis. *Journal of Educational and Social Research*, 10(4), 229–237. <https://doi.org/10.36941/JESR-2020-0080>
- Symonds, J. E., Kaplan, A., Upadyaya, K., Aro, K. S., Torsney, B. M., & Skinner, EllenEccles, J. S. (2019). *Momentary Student Engagement as a Dynamic Developmental System*. 1–53. <https://doi.org/10.31234/osf.io/fuy7p.2>
- Tambunan, H., Sinaga, B., & Widada, W. (2021). Analysis of Teacher Performance to Build Student Interest and Motivation towards Mathematics Achievement. *International Journal of Evaluation and Research in Education*, 10(1), 42-47.
- Tella, A. (2007). The impact of motivation on student's academic achievement and learning outcomes in mathematics among secondary school students in Nigeria. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education*, 3(2), 149-156.
- Tindan, T. N., Abukari, M. A., Antwi, V., Dorsah, P., & Kwakye, D. O. (2022). Contribution of intrinsic and extrinsic factors to teacher motivation. *International Education Studies and Sustainability*, 2(2), 19-28. <https://doi.org/10.2258/less.v2n2p19>
- Tindan, T. N., Abukari, M. A., Antwi, V., Dorsah, P., & Kwakye, D. O. (2023). Gender perspective of interpersonal relationships in pre-tertiary schools as a teacher motivator. *Mediterranean Journal of Social Sciences*, 14(1), 67-77. <https://doi.org/10.36941/mjss-2023-0007>
- Tindog, L. R. T. (2021). Contextualized Module with Mobile Applications and Learners' Mathematics Performance. *Journal of Science & Mathematics Education in Southeast Asia*, 44.
- Trochim, W. M. (2006). *The research methods knowledge base* (3rd ed.). Atomic Dog Publishing
- Trochim, W. M., & Donnelly, J. P. (2001). *Research methods knowledge base* (Vol. 2). Atomic Dog Publishers. https://www.researchgate.net/profile/William-Trochim/publication/243783609_The_Research_Methods_Knowledge_Base/links/55db837008aed
- Valenzuela, H. (2018). A Multiple Case Study of College-Contextualized Mathematics Curriculum. *Online Submission*, 9(2), 49-55.
- Wang, M., Binning, K. R., Toro, J. Del, Qin, X., & Zepeda, C. D. (2021). Skill , Thrill , and Will : The Role of Metacognition , Interest , and Self-Control in Predicting Student Engagement in Mathematics Learning Over Time. *Child Development*, 00(0), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1111/cdev.13531>
- Wang, M. T., & Holcombe, R. (2010). Adolescents' perceptions of school environment, engagement, and academic achievement in middle school. *American Educational Research Journal*, 47(3), 633–662. <https://doi.org/10.3102/0002831209361209>

Xia, Q., Yin, H., Hu, R., Li, X., & Shang, J. (2022). Motivation, Engagement, and Mathematics Achievement: An Exploratory Study Among Chinese Primary Students. *SAGE Open*, 12(4), 21582440221134609.

Zimmerman, B. J., & Schunk, D. H. (2012). Motivation: An essential dimension of self-regulated learning. In *Motivation and self-regulated learning* (pp. 1-30). Routledge.

